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Random and Fixed Effects of Wheat Genotypes Compared by Rank Based Measures: Northern Hills Zone

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Abstract

Rank based measures of stability based on random effects of wheat genotypes for the first year of study, S_i^s measures identified G11, G12, G1, G22 would be stable yield. Corrected yield measures CS_i^s selected G12, G17, G19, G21, G22 genotypes as possessing for stable yield. $NP_i^{(s)}$ identified G4, G12, G19, G22 as desirable genotypes for this zone. Kendall's coefficient of concordance expressed dependence among measures for ranking of wheat genotypes. Association analysis observed positive correlations of S_i^s , CS_i^s & $NP_i^{(s)}$ with other measures. Biplot analysis observed largest cluster comprised of CSD, CCV, S_i^1 , SD, S_i^5 , S_i^7 , CS_i^1 , CS_i^2 , CS_i^3 , CS_i^4 , CS_i^5 , CS_i^6 , CS_i^7 , Z1, Z2 measures. Fixed effects of genotypes, measures S_i^s found G2, G11, G21, G22 as suitable genotypes. Values of CS_i^s identified G3, G9, G21, G22 as compared to G3, G11, G19, G22 by $NP_i^{(s)}$ measures. Positive correlations exhibited by S_i^s , CS_i^s , $NP_i^{(s)}$ with values of other measures. Values of Kendall coefficient observed dependence among ranking of genotypes. Biplot graphical analysis seen affinity of CV with $NP_i^{(2)}$, $NP_i^{(3)}$, $NP_i^{(4)}$, S_i^3 , S_i^6 & CS_i^3 in graphical analysis. Measures settled for G1, G2, G5, G7 genotypes as per random effects for second year of study (2017-18). G1, G5, G7 by CS_i^s values whereas $NP_i^{(s)}$ settled G1, G2, G5, G7 genotypes of stable performance. Measures S_i^s , CS_i^s , $NP_i^{(s)}$ exhibited direct relationships with other rank based measures. Larger consisted of S_i^1 , S_i^2 , S_i^3 , S_i^5 , S_i^7 , CCV, CSD, $NP_i^{(1)}$, S_i^7 , CS_i^1 , CS_i^2 , CS_i^3 , CS_i^4 , CS_i^5 , CS_i^6 measures in biplot graphical analysis. Wheat genotypes G1, G4, G5, G7 identified by S_i^s measures considering BLUE estimates whereas G1, G5, G7 favoured by CS_i^s . Least values of $NP_i^{(s)}$ settled for G1, G5, G4. Direct relations expressed by S_i^s , CS_i^s & $NP_i^{(s)}$ measures. Larger cluster among four groups comprised of large cluster of S_i^1 , S_i^2 , S_i^4 , S_i^5 , S_i^7 , CCV, CSD, $NP_i^{(1)}$, CS_i^1 , CS_i^2 , CS_i^3 , CS_i^4 , CS_i^5 , CS_i^6 , CS_i^7 measures as last group.

Keywords : BLUP, BLUE, $S_i^{(s)}$, $CS_i^{(s)}$, $NP_i^{(s)}$, Coefficient of concordance, Biplot analysis

INTRODUCTION

Multi environments trials for the recommendation of high yielder wheat genotypes have been performed in number of research locations to represent broad environmental conditions (Igrejas & Branlard, 2020). The same set of genotypes exhibit variations in the performance as per different environmental conditions of research locations (Smith *et al.*, 2019). This fluctuation may be due to the genetic makeup, environmental vagaries and genotype $\times$ environment (G $\times$ E) interaction (Edicleide *et al.*, 2019). Cross over interaction effects may lead to inconsistency in classification of genotypes (Sousa *et al.*, 2020). Numerous methods have been reported in the literature for stability of genotypes under multi-environment trials setup. Recently methods consider the random effect of genotypes have been suggested (Gabriel *et al.*, 2020). Currently Restricted Maximum Likelihood/Best Linear Unbiased Prediction (REML/BLUP) based on mixed model had been established as an efficient analytic procedure (Souza *et al.*, 2019). Two major approaches for the stability analysis of genotypes had been mentioned (Pour-Aboughadareh *et al.*, 2019). First, most commonly used, approach known as parametric with presumed distributions of genotypic, environmental, and linear effects. Other approach called non-parametric which had no assumptions. Non-parametric procedures proposed based on the ranks of genotypes in each

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environment, and the genotypes with similar ranking across environments were classified as stable (Vaezi *et al.*, 2018). Good number of rank based measures has been developed to determine whether evaluated genotypes possessed the stable performance (Karimizadeh *et al.*, 2012; Mortazavian and Azizinia 2014; Van *et al.*, 2016 ; Khalili *et al.*, 2016). The present study was carried out with the objectives (1) analyze stable yield behaviour by rank based measures using random and fixed genotypes values (2) to differentiate the yield and stable pattern of genotypes vis-à-vis random and fixed effects and (3) study the relationships, similarities and dissimilarities among non-parametric measures of stability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Twenty four promising wheat genotypes were evaluated in research field trials at 6 centers of All India Coordinated Research Project on Wheat across Northern Hills Zone of the country during 2016-17 and seven genotypes were tested at research fields of ten centers during 2017-18 cropping season. Field trials were laid out in Randomized block designs with fore replications. Recommended practices of packages had followed in total to harvest the good yield. Parentage details and environmental conditions were reflected in tables 1 & 2 for ready reference. Huehn (1990 a & b) proposed seven nonparametric methods for assessing GxE interaction and stability analysis. For a two-way dataset with k genotypes and n environments X_{ij} denotes the phenotypic value of ith genotype in jth environment where $i=1,2, \dots,k, , j = 1,2, \dots, n$ and r_{ij} as the rank of the ith genotype in the jth environment, and $\bar{r}_i$ as the mean rank across all environments for the ith genotype. Sabaghnia *et al.*, (2012) proposed the correction for yield of ith genotype in jth environment as $(X^*_{ij} = X_{ij} - \bar{X}_{i..} + \bar{X}_{..})$ as X^*_{ij} , was the corrected phenotypic value; $\bar{X}_{i..}$ mean of ith genotype in all environments and $\bar{X}_{..}$ the grand mean. Generally used seven statistics based on ranks of genotypes yield and corrected yield were expressed as follows:

$$S_i^{(1)} = \frac{2 \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j'=j+1}^n |r_{ij} - r_{ij'}|}{[n(n-1)]} \quad S_i^{(7)} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij} - \bar{r}_i)^2}{\sum_{j=1}^n |r_{ij} - \bar{r}_i|} \quad S_i^{(3)} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij} - \bar{r}_i)^2}{\bar{r}_i}$$

$$S_i^{(4)} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij} - \bar{r}_i)^2}{n}} \quad S_i^{(5)} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n |r_{ij} - \bar{r}_i|}{n} \quad S_i^{(6)} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n |r_{ij} - \bar{r}_i|}{\bar{r}_i}$$

$$S_i^{(2)} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij} - \bar{r}_i)^2}{(n-1)} \quad \bar{r}_i = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n r_{ij} \quad Z_i^{(v)} = \frac{[S_i^{(v)} - E\{S_i^{(v)}\}]^2}{Var\{S_i^{(v)}\}}, v = 1,2$$

Measures $NP_i^{(1)}$, $NP_i^{(2)}$, $NP_i^{(3)}$ and $NP_i^{(4)}$ based on ranks of corrected yield of genotypes proposed by Thennarasu (1995) for stability analysis. In the formulas, r^*_{ij} was the rank of X^*_{ij} , and $\bar{r}_i$ and M_{di} were the mean and median of ranks as per original yield values, where $\bar{r}_i^*$ and M_{di}^* were the same parameters computed from the corrected yield values.

$$NP_i^{(1)} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n |r^*_{ij} - M_{di}^*| \quad NP_i^{(3)} = \frac{\sqrt{\sum (r^*_{ij} - \bar{r}_i^*)^2 / n}}{\bar{r}_i}$$

$$NP_i^{(2)} = \frac{1}{n} \left(\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n |r^*_{ij} - M_{di}^*|}{M_{di}^*} \right) \quad NP_i^{(4)} = \frac{2}{n(n-1)} \left[\sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j'=j+1}^n \frac{|r^*_{ij} - r^*_{ij'}|}{\bar{r}_i} \right]$$

Significance of $S_i^{(1)}$ and $S_i^{(2)}$ non parametric measures had been explored by Nassar and Huehn (1987). Z1 and Z2 values were calculated for each genotype, based on the ranks of adjusted data and then sum up i.e. Z1 sum and Z2 sum as distributed χ^2 . Degree of similarity among measures had assessed by estimating correlation coefficients while considering genotypes ranking. Spearman’s rank correlation values estimated as follows (Piepho and Lotito, 1992) :

$$\bar{r}_s = 1 - \frac{6 \sum_{i=1}^n d_i^2}{n(n^2-1)} ; d_i - \text{difference between ranks for ith genotype and n is total number of pairs.}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**Analytic analysis based on Random effects of genotypes 2016-17**

Average yield of genotypes identified G14, G1, G2, whereas GAI selected G1, G2, G20 genotypes (Mohammadi and Amri, 2008), large values of Median observed for G5, G13, G8 (table 3). Three descriptive statistics: mean of ranks (MR), standard deviation of ranks (SD) and coefficient of variation of ranks (CV) considered G5, G7, G11; G1, G22, G21; G12, G22, G24 respectively. These descriptive statistics based on ranks can be used for genotype comparative evaluation. Karimizadeh *et al.*, (2012) proposed two ranking methods according to mean and standard deviation of ranks. The advantages of these rank based procedures in phenotypic stability studies had reported by Farshadfar *et al.*, 2014 & Khalili *et al.*, 2016). First two S_i^1 S_i^2 measures selected G1, G22, G21 as opposed to G11, G12, G16 by S_i^3 . G1, G22, G21 considered by S_i^4 and S_i^5 selected for G1, G12, G22, S_i^6 pointed towards G12, G22, G11 genotypes while S_i^7 favoured G21, G22, G1 wheat genotypes. Mean of ranks as per corrected yield values selected G2, G1, G13; G21 G19 G22 by corrected standard deviation & Coefficient of variation observed suitability of G21, G22, G19 genotypes. Corrected median values Cmed observed suitability of G13, G1, G2. Genotypes G21, G19, G22 marked by CS_i^1 & while G21, G17, G12 by CS_i^3 and CS_i^4 pointed G21, G19, G22 ; CS_i^5 for G21, G22, G6; G21, G22, G12 as per CS_i^6 and lastly by CS_i^7 G19, G21, G22 as suitable for considered locations of the zone (Sabaghnia *et al.*, 2012). The mentioned measures determine the stability of genotype over environment if its rank is similar over other environments (biological concept). Many authors that have used the Huehn's (1990 a & b) nonparametric measures of phenotypic stability and demonstrated that these measures were associated with the biological concept of stability (Ahmadi *et al.*, 2015; Farshadfar *et al.*, 2014). Rank based measures $NP_i^{(1)}$ for (G21, G6, G22), $NP_i^{(2)}$ selected (G12, G4, G22), $NP_i^{(3)}$ for (G22, G12, G19), $NP_i^{(4)}$ considered (G12, G22, G19) genotypes of choice whereas values of measures Z1 observed G20, G11, G16 and genotypes G20, G1, G16 by Z2 values.

Kendall's coefficient of concordance, W was used to assess the degree of agreement among rank based measures. Value of $W = 1$ indicates a perfect agreement among rankings by measures across the environments, and while $W = 0$ indicates total disagreement (Vazei *et al.*, 2018). Calculated values of $W = 0.48$ and for its significance values of χ^2 statistic = 332.39. Calculated value was more than table of χ^2 (0.05, 23) = 19.1, which resulted dependence among rank based measures. Z1 and Z2 values were calculated for each genotype as per the ranks based on of corrected yield values and then summed to calculate Z_1 sum = 23.52 and Z_2 sum = 19.10 (Table 3). Both values were less than the critical value of χ^2 (0.05, 23) = 35.2. This indicated the non-significant differences among genotypes as per ranks by CS_i^1 and CS_i^2 measures. Individual Z values of G4, G5, G8, G7, G12, G13 & G18 were more than the critical value of χ^2 (0.05, 1) = 3.84 to reflect their unstable yield.

Correlation analysis

Spearman's correlation analysis observed highly significant, significant positive and negative relationships of Yield (Kilic *et al.*, 2010). Significant association values seen with GAI, MR, CV, Med, S_i^6 , $NP_i^{(2)}$, $NP_i^{(3)}$, $NP_i^{(4)}$. GAI expressed highly significant negative correlations with MR, CV, Med, S_i^6 , $NP_i^{(2)}$, $NP_i^{(4)}$ along with positive values of low magnitude (table 7). MR exhibited highly significant direct relationships with CV, Med, S_i^6 , $NP_i^{(2)}$, $NP_i^{(3)}$, $NP_i^{(4)}$. Highly significant positive correlation and positive correlation values observed for SD with measures. CV had expressed direct relationships with measures. Med had maintained weak negative correlation and positive with only S_i^3 , S_i^6 , $NP_i^{(2)}$, $NP_i^{(3)}$, $NP_i^{(4)}$. Highly significant to significant relationships had maintained by S_i^1 , S_i^2 , S_i^3 , S_i^4 , S_i^5 , S_i^6 , S_i^7 with others and themselves in direct manner. Descriptive measures as per corrected yield of genotypes (CMR, CSD, CCV, Cmed) had achieved only positive relations of strong to moderate types. Apart from negative values of low magnitude with CV measure, only positive associations extended by CS_i^1 , CS_i^2 , CS_i^3 , CS_i^4 , CS_i^5 , CS_i^6 , CS_i^7 with others and themselves. Direct relations of significant nature with most of measures settled by $NP_i^{(1)}$, $NP_i^{(2)}$, $NP_i^{(3)}$, $NP_i^{(4)}$ values. Z1 and Z2 measures were able to maintain direct relationships with negative values of low magnitude with MR, CV, $NP_i^{(2)}$, $NP_i^{(3)}$, $NP_i^{(4)}$.

Biplot graphical analysis

Table 8 shows the loading of the first two PCA of rank based measures of stability for wheat genotypes, accounting for 77.6% of the variance of the original variables (Mohammadi *et al.*, 2016). The PCA1 versus PCA2 were used to generate the biplot illustrated in Fig. 1. According to the biplot, the first PC1 and PC2 main axes grouped GAI with yield, MR with Med and CMR with Cmed. Measures CV, NP_i⁽³⁾, S_i³, NP_i⁽²⁾, NP_i⁽⁴⁾, S_i⁶ grouped together and remaining measures CSD, CCV, S_i¹, SD, S_i⁵, S_i⁷, CS_i¹, CS_i², CS_i³, CS_i⁴, CS_i⁵, CS_i⁶, CS_i⁷, Z1, Z2 comprised in larger cluster.

Analytic analysis based on fixed effects of genotypes 2016-17

Higher mean yield observed for G1 genotype was the highest yielding with 31.9q/ha followed by G14 and G2 (Table 4). Measure GAI selected G1, G2, G20 as genotypes with higher adaptable index values. Three descriptive statistics; mean of ranks (MR), standard deviation of ranks (SD) and coefficient of variation of ranks (CV) pointed towards G5, G11, G7; G22, G2, G21 & G22, G5, G11 as genotypes of stable performance respectively, while G14, G2 based on MR; G13, G14 based on SD and G14, G17 based on CV, would be genotypes of unstable behavior. Median selected G4, G13, G8 wheat genotypes. Measures S_i¹, S_i² pointed for G22, G2, G21; G11, G12, G9 by S_i³, G22, G2, G21 by S_i⁴, G22, G19, G2 as per S_i⁵ values however G22, G11, G5 by S_i⁶ and G22, G2, G21 by S_i⁷ would achieve stable yield. Genotypes G16, G1 & G2 would be of choice as per mean of ranks (CMR), G22, G21 & G3 by standard deviation (CSD) & coefficient of variation (CCV). Measures considered ranks as per corrected yield CS_i¹, CS_i², CS_i³, CS_i⁴, CS_i⁵, CS_i⁶, CS_i⁷ (G22, G21, G3; G22, G21, G3; G9, G22, G21; G22, G21, G3; G22, G21, G3; G22, G21, G3) as stable genotypes. Values of NP_i⁽¹⁾ settled for G22, G21, G3 genotypes as compared to the other genotypes. The genotypes G22, G19 and G11 had the lower value of NP_i⁽²⁾, whereas as per NP_i⁽³⁾ & NP_i⁽⁴⁾ genotypes of choice would be G22, G11, G19. Measure Z1 pointed for G20, G6, G1 and Z2 expressed confidence for G6, G4, G12 wheat genotypes.

Kendall's coefficient of concordance, $W = 0.43$ and for its significance $\chi^2 = 295.19$ was more than table of χ^2 (0.05, 23) = 35.2 resulted dependence among rank based measures. Z1 and Z2 values were calculated for each genotype and then summed: Z₁ sum = 11.93 and Z₂ sum = 12.09 (Table 6). Both these statistics distributed as χ^2 and were less than the critical value of χ^2 (0.05, 23) = 35.2. This indicated the non-significant differences among ranks of genotypes as per CS_i¹ & CS_i² measures. Individual Z values of G3, G7, G8, G13, G14 genotypes more than the critical value of χ^2 (0.05, 1) = 3.84 to show their unstable performance.

Correlation analysis showed unstable behaviour

Mean yield had expressed significant positive with GAI and negative correlation with (MR, CV, Med, S_i⁶, NP_i⁽²⁾, NP_i⁽³⁾, NP_i⁽⁴⁾) respectively (Table 9). GAI exhibited mostly significant negative values of correlations. Direct relations of significant nature had maintained by descriptive measure MR with weak indirect correlations also. SD showed significant direct relationships as only positive values were scanned. CV expressed similar type of relationships with measures. More over Med exhibited mostly negative relationships except of positive with S_i³, S_i⁶, NP_i⁽²⁾, NP_i⁽³⁾ & NP_i⁽⁴⁾. Except of small negative values with MR, CV, Med measures S_i¹, S_i², S_i³, S_i⁴, S_i⁵, S_i⁶, S_i⁷ maintained direct relationships with other measures. Descriptive measures based on ranks as per corrected yield values (CMR, CSD, CCV) expressed only direct relationships. Defined measures CS_i¹, CS_i², CS_i³, CS_i⁴, CS_i⁵, CS_i⁶, CS_i⁷ showed positive correlations among themselves and others except of Med. Indirect weak correlation with Z1 and Z2, all positive correlations achieved by NP_i⁽¹⁾, NP_i⁽²⁾, NP_i⁽³⁾, NP_i⁽⁴⁾. Lastly Z1 and Z2 expressed mostly direct correlation except of negative correlation values with Med & NP_i⁽²⁾.

Biplot graphical analysis

In order to explore possible association among rank based measures of stability biplot graphical analysis had been used. Loadings of the measures as per first two principal components axes (PCA) were shown in table 10. Both significant PAC's accounted for 74.7% of the variations of the original variables. Small clusters of Yield

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with GAI, MR with Med & CMR with Cmed were observed. Measure CV clubbed with $NP_i^{(2)}$, $NP_i^{(3)}$, $NP_i^{(4)}$, S_i^3 , S_i^6 & CS_i^3 in graphical analysis. Left over measures SD, CSD, Cmed, CMR, Z1, Z2, CCV, $NP_i^{(1)}$, S_i^1 , S_i^2 , S_i^3 , S_i^4 , S_i^5 , S_i^6 , S_i^7 , CS_i^1 , CS_i^2 , CS_i^4 , CS_i^5 , CS_i^7 joined together in last cluster.

Analytic analysis based on Random effects of genotypes 2017-18

Average yield of genotypes identified G7, G6, G1, whereas GAI selected G7, G3, G5 genotypes, large values of Median observed for G4, G6, G2. Three descriptive measures of ranks: mean of ranks (MR), standard deviation of ranks (SD) and coefficient of variation of ranks (CV) were calculated as per ranks for original yield values. Genotypes were of choice G2, G4, G6 by MR. Consistent yield of G1, G5, G7 genotypes expressed by lower values of standard deviation (Table 5) while G1, G5, G2 pointed by coefficient of variation. Measures S_i^1 , S_i^2 , S_i^3 , S_i^4 , S_i^5 & S_i^7 selected G1, G5, G7 opposed to G1, G5, G2 considered by S_i^6 values. Descriptive measures as per ranks of genotypes by corrected yield settled for G6, G7, G1 & G1, G5, G7 by CMR and CSD along with CCV. Median of ranks as per corrected yield values selected G2, G4, G6. Unanimously genotypes G1, G5, G7 marked by all CS_i^5 measures as suitable for considered locations of the zone. Rank based measures $NP_i^{(1)}$ for (G1, G5, G7), $NP_i^{(2)}$ selected (G1, G5, G6), $NP_i^{(3)}$ & $NP_i^{(4)}$ for (G1, G5, G2) genotypes simultaneously by original and corrected values. Z1 and Z2 values observed G7, G2, G3 as genotypes of choice.

Calculated values of $W = 0.48$ and for its significance values of χ^2 statistic = 87.1 was more than corresponding table of χ^2 at 5% level of significance. Implied an overall similarity among rank based measures. Values of Z_1 sum = 14.68 and Z_2 sum = 16.06 were less than the critical value of $\chi^2(0.01, 6) = 16.8$. This indicated the non-significant differences among genotypes as per ranks of CS_i^1 and CS_i^2 measures. More over the Z values showed G1, G5 were significantly unstable as as Z values more than the critical value of $\chi^2(0.05, 1) = 3.84$.

Correlation analysis

Positive correlation of yield had observed with GAI, SD, CV, S_i^1 , S_i^2 , S_i^4 , S_i^5 , S_i^7 , CSD, CCV, CS_i^1 , CS_i^2 , CS_i^3 , CS_i^4 , CS_i^5 , CS_i^6 , CS_i^7 , $NP_i^{(1)}$, $NP_i^{(2)}$, $NP_i^{(3)}$, $NP_i^{(4)}$, Z1, Z2 and negative values with MR, Med, Cmed only (Table 11). GAI showed negative correlations with MR, Med, CV, Cmed, $NP_i^{(2)}$, $NP_i^{(3)}$, $NP_i^{(4)}$ and positive with SD, S_i^1 , S_i^2 , S_i^4 , S_i^5 , S_i^7 , CCV, CS_i^1 , CS_i^2 , CS_i^3 , CS_i^4 , CS_i^5 , CS_i^6 , CS_i^7 , $NP_i^{(1)}$. Descriptive measure MR expressed small negative values of correlation with SD, S_i^1 , S_i^2 , S_i^4 , S_i^5 , S_i^7 , CS_i^1 , CS_i^2 , CS_i^3 , CS_i^4 , CS_i^5 , CS_i^6 , CS_i^7 , $NP_i^{(1)}$, Z1, Z2 and positive values with CV, Med, Cmed, $NP_i^{(2)}$, $NP_i^{(3)}$, $NP_i^{(4)}$. Next SD maintained highly significant and significant direct relations with almost all the measures exception of Med, Cmed, Z1, Z2. Significant positive correlation showed by CV with measures and negative correlations with Z1, Z2. Med had achieved indirect correlations with 21 measures and positive correlations Cmed, $NP_i^{(2)}$. Indirect relations with Cmed, Z1 & Z2 values S_i^1 , S_i^2 , S_i^3 , S_i^4 , S_i^5 , S_i^6 , S_i^7 had positive correlations with measures. Descriptive measures used ranks of genotypes as per corrected yield values showed direct relations of significant nature and of negative correlations with Z1, Z2. CMed had achieved mostly indirect type relationships. CS_i^1 , CS_i^2 , CS_i^3 , CS_i^4 , CS_i^5 , CS_i^6 , CS_i^7 behaved in similar fashion as expressed positive relationships with most of measures exception of Cmed, Z1, Z2. The measures $NP_i^{(1)}$, $NP_i^{(2)}$, $NP_i^{(3)}$, $NP_i^{(4)}$ had expressed positive correlations with measures with negative correlations of MR, Med, Z1, Z2. Mostly inverse relationships exhibited by Z1 and Z2.

Biplot graphical analysis

Association among rank based measures of stability had been studied by Biplot graphical analysis. First two significant PAC's accounting for 88.9% of the variations of the original variables. Loading of rank based measures were reflected in table 12. The PCA1 versus PCA2 were used to generate five clusters in the graphical analysis (figure 3). Yield had grouped with GAI, CMR, Cmed, Z1 with Z2 and MR with Med were seen. CV expressed close affinity with SD, CV, $NP_i^{(2)}$, $NP_i^{(3)}$, $NP_i^{(4)}$, S_i^6 , CS_i^7 measures & last group consisted of S_i^1 , S_i^2 , S_i^3 , S_i^5 , S_i^7 , CCV, CSD, $NP_i^{(1)}$, S_i^7 , CS_i^1 , CS_i^2 , CS_i^3 , CS_i^4 , CS_i^5 , CS_i^6 measures.

Analytic analysis based on fixed effects of genotypes 2017-18

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Higher average yield observed for G7 genotype was the highest yielding with 28.2 q/ha followed by G5 and G3 (Table 6). Larger values of index GAI selected G7, G3, G5 genotypes. Three descriptive statistics; mean of ranks (MR), standard deviation of ranks (SD) & coefficient of variation of ranks (CV) pointed for G1, G4, G3; G1, G7, G5 & G1, G4, G2 genotypes respectively, while G7, G5 based on MR; G3, G2 based on SD and G5, G6 based on CV, would be genotypes of unstable behavior. Values of Median measures selected G4, G1, G2 wheat genotypes. Next measures $S_i^1, S_i^2, S_i^3, S_i^4, S_i^5, S_i^6, S_i^7$ settled for G1, G7, G5 ; G1, G7, G5 ; G1, G4, G7; G1, G7, G5; G1, G7, G5 ; G1, G4, G2 ; G1, G7, G4 respectively. According to ranks as per corrected yield values (table 6), genotypes G6, G7, G1 would be of choice as per mean of ranks (CMR), G1, G5 , G7 by standard deviation (CSD) & coefficient of variation (CCV). Measures based on ranks as per corrected yield values of genotypes ($CS_i^1, CS_i^2, CS_i^3, CS_i^4, CS_i^5, CS_i^6, CS_i^7$) favoured G1, G5, G7 genotypes as stable performance. $NP_i^{(6)}$ settled for G1, G5, G4 genotypes as compared to G7 and G3. Z1 and Z2 had pointed for G7, G4, G5 and G4, G7, G5 wheat genotypes respectively.

Value of $W = 0.44$ and for its significance $\chi^2 = 79.57$ was more than table of $\chi^2 (0.05, 6) = 16.8$ resulted dependence among rank based measures. Values Z_1 sum = 14.68 and Z_2 sum = 16.06 were less than the critical value of $\chi^2(0.01, 6) = 16.8$. This indicated the non-significant differences among genotypes as per ranks of CS_i^1 and CS_i^2 measures. Unstable behaviour of G1, G3 of genotypes verified by individual Z values more with respect to critical value.

Correlation analysis

Yield had expressed positive correlation with GAI, SD, CMR, $S_i^1, S_i^2, S_i^4, S_i^5$, CSD, CCV, Cmed, Z1, Z2, $NP_i^{(1)}$, $CS_i^1, CS_i^2, CS_i^3, CS_i^4, CS_i^5, CS_i^6, CS_i^7$ and negative with MR, CV, $NP_i^{(2)}, NP_i^{(3)}$ and $NP_i^{(4)}$. Significant indirect relations were expressed by GAI with measures though non-significant positive values were also shown (Table 13). Descriptive measures based on ranks of genotypes as per yield values MR had both types of relationships; SD had achieved only direct relations of significant nature; CV able to maintain both types but direct relations were of significant type. Med. expressed significant positive correlations with measures, while weak negative with CMed, Z1, Z2 etc. Med had mostly negative correlation values whereas significant values had positive nature. Measures $S_i^1, S_i^2, S_i^3, S_i^4, S_i^5, S_i^6, S_i^7$ maintained only direct relationships with strong to moderate values. Descriptive measure as corrected yield values i.e. CMR maintained nature of correlation with negative values for $NP_i^{(1)}, NP_i^{(2)}, NP_i^{(3)}, NP_i^{(4)}$, Z1, Z2 measures. Highly significant direct relationships shown by CSD except with Z1, Z2. Measure CCV had behaved in similar manner to CSD. Cmed had indirect values of correlation with $NP_i^{(2)}, NP_i^{(3)}, NP_i^{(4)}$. Except of negative correlation with Med only positive correlations had achieved by $CS_i^1, CS_i^2, CS_i^3, CS_i^4, CS_i^5, CS_i^6, CS_i^7, NP_i^{(1)}, NP_i^{(2)}, NP_i^{(3)}, NP_i^{(4)}$ measures. Weak and strong correlations of both types had maintained by Z1 & Z2 measures.

Biplot graphical analysis

Loading of rank based measures of stability for wheat genotypes were reflected in table 14 as first two significant PAC's accounting for 80.9% of the variations of the original variables . Four groups of measures observed in the graphical analysis as per PCA1 versus PCA2 values (figure 4). GAI had grouped with CMR, Cmed whereas Z1, MR with Med in small clusters. CV expressed close affinity with $NP_i^{(2)}, NP_i^{(3)}, NP_i^{(4)}, S_i^3, S_i^6, CS_i^7$ measures & large cluster of $S_i^1, S_i^2, S_i^4, S_i^5, S_i^7, CCV, CSD, NP_i^{(1)}, CS_i^1, CS_i^2, CS_i^3, CS_i^4, CS_i^5, CS_i^6, CS_i^7$ measures as last group.

CONCLUSIONS

Rank based measures of stability for wheat genotypes as per BLUP/REML provide more valid yield estimates under multi environment trials. As more variations accounted by first two significant principal components by rank based measures. Lesser number of clusters (3 to 4) in biplot graphical analysis expressed good cohesive bonds among studied measures. Strong and positive correlations of $S_i^5, CS_i^5, NP_i^{(5)}$ measures among themselves

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vis-à-vis with others showed independence of ranks of genotypes either based on original and corrected yield values. Values of Kendall coefficient of concordance expressed the similarity among ranking of genotypes as per original and corrected yield values. Mostly significant positive and negative relationships exhibited by Spearman's rank correlation values among measures.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

No conflict of interest among authors for this study.

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Table 1: Parentage details of genotypes and environmental conditions of locations (2016-17)

Code	Genotyp Parentage	Cod e	Location s	Latitude	Longitu de	Altitu de
G 1	HS631 (WHEAR/VIVITSI/WHEAR)	E 1	Almora	29° 35 ' N	79° 39 ' E	1610
G 2	HS632 (HS240*2/FLW20(LR19)//HS240*2/FLW13(YR15)	E 2	Khudwa ni	33° 70' N	75°10' E	1590
G 3	HS633 (HS240*2/FLW20(LR19)//HS240*2/FLW13(YR15)	E 3	Malan	32°08 ' N	76°35'E	846
G 4	HS634 (PBW343*2/KUKUNA/5/CNO79//PF73054/MUS/3/PASTOR/4/BAV92)	E 4	Shimla	31°10 ' N	77°17'E	2276
G 5	HS635 (PFAU/MILAN/5/CHEN/AE.SQUARROSA(TAUS)//BCN/3/VEE#7/BOW/4/PASTOR)	E 5	Bajaura	31°84 ' N	77°16' E	1099
G 6	HS636 (PASTOR//KAUZ/6/CNDO/R143//ENTE/MEX1-2/3/AEGILOPSSQUARROSA(TAUS)/4/WEAVER/5/2*KAUZ)	E 6	Wadura	21° 18' N	77° 41' E	508
G 7	HS637 (PRL/2*PASTOR)					
G 8	HPW 441 (NAC/TH.AC//3*MIRLO/BUC/4/PASTOR)					
G 9	HPW44 2 (LONG291*2/PASTOR)					
G 10	HPW44 3 (PASTOR//HXL7573/2*BAU/3/SOKOLL/WBLL1)					
G 11	HPW44 4 (AZAR2/4/CROC_1/AE.SQUARROSA (205)//BORL95/3/2*MILAN/5/BERKUT)					
G 12	HPW44 5 (PBW575/HPW251)					
G 13	HPW44 6 (BOW/URES//KEA/3/SITE)					
G 14	HPW44 7 (HPW266/HPW249)					
G 15	VL 2025 (LBPY04-1/RAJ4132//HS490)					
G 16	VL 2026 (GW366/KS82W428/SWM75740//UP2739)					
G 17	VL 2027 (RAJ4083/SKAUZ/HATUSA//VL900)					
G 18	VL 2028 (FRANCOLIN#1*2/MUU)					
G 19	VL 2029 (MUNAL#1/FRANCOLIN#1)					
G 20	VL2030 (KA/NAC//TRCH/3/DANPHE#1)					
G 21	UP2990 (UP2744/WL711//PBW644)					
G 22	UP2991 (SOKOLL/3/PASTOR//HXL7573/2*BAU/4/SOKOLL/WBLL1)					
G 23	VL 907 (DYBR1982-8384ABVD50/VW9365//PBW343)					
G 24	HS 507 (KAUZ/MYNA/VUL//BUC/FLK/4/MILAN)					

Table 2: Parentage details of genotypes and environmental conditions of locations (2017-18)

Code	Genotype	Parentage	Code	Locations	Latitude	Longitude	Altitude
G 1	HPW 349	(NAC/TH.AC//3*MIRLO/BUC/4/2*PASTOR)	E 1	Akrot	31°4 ' N	76°1' E	425
G 2	HS 634	(PBW343*2/KUKUNA/5/CNO79//PF73054/MUS/3/PASTOR/4/BAV92)	E 2	Almora	29° 35 ' N	79° 39 ' E	1610
G 3	VL 907	(DYBR1982-8384ABVD50/VW9365//PBW343)	E 3	Bajaura	31°84 ' N	77°16' E	1099
G 4	HS 507	(KAUZ/MYNA/VUL//BUC/FLK/4/MILAN)	E 4	Berthin	31°50' N	77°9' E	1103
G 5	HPW 441	(NAC/TH.AC//3*MIRLO/BUC/4/PASTOR)	E 5	Daulakuan	30°16 ' N	74°56'E	468
G 6	HPW 442	(LONG291*2/PASTOR)	E 6	Khudwani	33° 70' N	75°10' E	1590
G 7	HS 562	(OASIS/SKUAZ//4*BCN/3/2*PASTOR)	E 7	Majhera	29° 16' N	80° 5' E	1532
			E 8	Malan	32°08' N	76°35'E	846
			E 9	Ranichauri	28° 43' N	81°02 ' E	2200
			E 10	Shimla	31°10 ' N	77°17'E	2276

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Table 3: Rank based measures of stability as per original and corrected yield values for random effects of genotypes (2016-17)

Genotype	Yield	GAI	MR	SD	CV	Med	S _i ¹	S _i ²	S _i ³	S _i ⁴	S _i ⁵	S _i ⁶	S _i ⁷	CM	CSD	CCV	Cmed	CS _i ¹	CS _i ²	CS _i ³	CS _i ⁴	CS _i ⁵	CS _i ⁶	CS _i ⁷	NP _i ⁽¹⁾	NP _i ⁽²⁾	NP _i ⁽³⁾	NP _i ⁽⁴⁾	Z1	Z2
HS631	31.6 2	30.6 7	6.83	3.06	0.45	7.50	3.27	9.37	1.47	3.06	1.9	1.7	4.01	14.0	6.69	0.48	16.50	7.07	44.80	1.7	6.69	4.6	2.0	8.00	4.0	0.53	2.19	1.0	0.05	0.53
HS632	31.4 6	30.5 5	7.67	5.32	0.69	7.00	6.40	28.27	5.23	5.32	4.6	3.6	5.05	14.6	7.26	0.49	16.50	8.53	52.67	3.6	7.26	5.4	2.2	8.06	5.0	0.71	2.12	1.1	0.02	1.23
HS633	29.0 7	28.0 8	11.1	7.57	0.68	11.5	9.27	57.37	5.97	7.57	6.1	3.3	7.75	11.1	7.52	0.67	10.50	9.00	56.57	4.6	7.52	6.1	3.3	7.64	6.1	0.54	1.51	0.8	0.06	4.09
HS634	29.2 0	28.1 1	14.0	6.36	0.45	16.0	7.60	40.40	1.14	6.36	5.0	2.1	6.73	13.6	5.24	0.38	15.00	6.40	27.47	0.4	5.24	4.1	1.8	5.57	4.0	0.25	0.84	0.4	0.15	22.85
HS635	26.6 7	25.6 8	18.5	5.65	0.31	20.0	6.33	31.90	0.12	5.65	4.0	1.3	6.65	11.8	8.33	0.70	9.00	9.93	69.37	3.9	8.33	6.7	3.4	8.53	6.5	0.33	1.01	0.5	0.23	25.14
HS636	28.8 9	28.1 0	12.5	5.36	0.43	10.5	5.53	28.70	0.98	5.36	3.6	1.7	6.52	10.8	5.67	0.52	9.50	5.80	32.17	0.3	5.67	3.7	2.0	7.20	3.1	0.30	1.01	0.4	0.29	13.55
HS637	27.5 0	27.0 0	16.8	8.13	0.48	18.0	9.27	66.17	3.05	8.13	5.5	1.9	9.93	13.5	9.07	0.67	12.00	10.8	82.30	8.1	9.07	7.0	3.1	9.80	6.5	0.36	1.21	0.6	0.50	64.59
HPW 441	27.9 5	27.4 5	16.0	8.02	0.50	18.5	9.60	64.40	2.25	8.02	6.6	2.5	8.05	11.6	9.79	0.84	11.50	11.7	95.87	3.4	9.79	8.6	4.4	9.22	8.6	0.47	1.37	0.7	0.85	125.6
HPW442	29.1 5	28.1 5	11.6	7.87	0.67	14.5	9.20	61.87	8.01	7.87	6.4	3.3	8.00	11.6	7.69	0.66	13.00	9.20	59.07	6.4	7.69	6.6	3.4	7.38	6.6	0.46	1.47	0.7	0.09	6.79
HPW443	28.7 3	27.5 8	12.8	8.18	0.64	10.5	9.80	66.97	2.65	8.18	6.8	3.1	8.17	12.1	8.61	0.71	9.50	10.2	74.17	3.1	8.61	7.1	3.5	8.62	7.1	0.68	1.50	0.7	0.30	37.65
HPW444	27.7 8	26.6 6	16.6	5.16	0.31	17.5	5.73	26.67	0.03	5.16	3.4	1.2	6.45	12.6	6.44	0.51	12.00	7.87	41.47	2.5	6.44	4.8	2.3	7.07	4.6	0.27	0.86	0.4	0.00	2.27
HPW445	28.4 1	27.8 1	16.3	4.03	0.25	16.5	4.53	16.27	0.03	4.03	2.6	0.9	5.08	13.1	5.31	0.40	12.50	6.33	28.17	0.1	5.31	3.8	1.7	6.04	3.8	0.23	0.73	0.3	0.17	21.31
HPW446	28.6 6	28.2 6	15.0	10.2	0.68	20.0	11.60	105.2	4.27	10.2	8.6	3.4	10.1	14.0	9.78	0.70	19.00	10.9	95.60	2.5	9.78	8.3	3.5	9.56	7.0	0.35	1.46	0.7	0.53	124.2
HPW447	31.6 3	29.6 5	6.67	8.91	1.34	3.50	9.20	79.47	4.82	8.91	5.8	5.3	11.2	10.1	9.33	0.92	8.50	11.2	86.97	6.5	9.33	7.8	4.6	9.25	7.8	2.24	3.13	1.6	0.65	83.31
VL 2025	30.2 9	29.6 2	11.1	8.26	0.74	9.50	9.93	68.17	8.66	8.26	6.5	3.5	8.67	13.8	8.66	0.63	14.50	10.6	74.97	6.0	8.66	6.8	2.9	9.14	6.8	0.72	1.73	0.9	0.41	39.97
VL 2026	30.1 3	29.0 6	11.3	5.72	0.50	13.0	6.93	32.67	0.04	5.72	4.5	2.4	5.98	13.8	7.17	0.52	16.50	8.47	51.37	0.7	7.17	5.8	2.5	7.27	5.1	0.40	1.41	0.7	0.01	0.65
VL 2027	30.1 0	29.1 7	9.17	8.40	0.92	5.00	9.53	70.57	2.91	8.40	6.8	4.5	8.54	12.0	8.20	0.68	9.50	9.87	67.20	0.0	8.20	6.6	3.3	8.40	6.3	1.27	2.00	1.0	0.21	20.31
VL 2028	27.6 3	26.3 6	14.5	8.36	0.58	14.5	10.20	69.90	6.22	8.36	7.1	2.9	8.13	10.8	10.2	0.94	7.50	12.0	104.5	8.9	10.2	8.4	4.6	10.3	7.8	0.54	1.58	0.8	1.01	175.3
VL 2029	28.8 1	27.8 8	13.6	4.55	0.33	13.0	5.47	20.67	2.35	4.55	3.5	1.5	4.84	12.1	4.49	0.37	12.00	5.53	20.17	1.4	4.49	3.8	1.8	4.38	3.8	0.29	0.73	0.4	0.36	42.07
VL2030	30.7 2	30.0 1	9.17	6.94	0.76	5.50	7.80	48.17	10.5	6.94	5.8	3.8	6.82	12.5	6.86	0.55	10.00	8.07	47.10	5.7	6.86	5.6	2.7	6.93	5.1	0.94	1.67	0.8	0.00	0.04
UP2990	29.9 0	29.0 8	9.50	3.67	0.39	10.0	4.47	13.50	1.29	3.67	3.1	2.0	3.55	13.0	4.05	0.31	13.50	4.93	16.40	0.0	4.05	3.0	1.3	4.56	3.0	0.30	0.95	0.5	0.56	54.27

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Table 5: Rank based measures of stability as per original and corrected yield values for random effects of genotypes (2017-18)

Genotype	Yield	GAI	MR	SD	CV	Med	S _i ¹	S _i ²	S _i ³	S _i ⁴	S _i ⁵	S _i ⁶	S _i ⁷	CMR	CSD	CCV	Cmed	CS _i ¹	CS _i ²	CS _i ³	CS _i ⁴	CS _i ⁵	CS _i ⁶	CS _i ⁷	NP _i ⁽¹⁾	NP _i ⁽²⁾	NP _i ⁽³⁾	NP _i ⁽⁴⁾	Z1	Z2
HPW 349	26.51	21.54	4.00	0.82	0.20	4.00	0.93	0.67	1.50	0.82	0.60	1.50	1.00	4.10	0.88	0.21	4.00	1.00	0.77	1.68	0.88	0.72	1.76	0.96	0.70	0.18	0.66	0.25	11.11	6.72
HS 634	26.28	20.24	4.40	2.32	0.53	4.50	2.76	5.38	11.00	2.32	2.00	4.55	2.42	4.10	2.28	0.56	4.00	2.69	5.21	11.44	2.28	1.92	4.68	2.44	1.90	0.42	1.56	0.61	1.09	0.94
VL 907	25.91	22.34	3.80	2.44	0.64	4.00	2.84	5.96	14.11	2.44	2.20	5.79	2.44	3.80	2.44	0.64	3.00	2.84	5.96	14.11	2.44	2.16	5.68	2.48	2.00	0.50	1.93	0.75	2.10	2.46
HS 507	25.66	21.16	4.30	2.71	0.63	5.50	3.09	7.34	15.37	2.71	2.44	5.67	2.71	3.50	2.59	0.74	3.00	3.00	6.72	17.29	2.59	2.30	6.57	2.63	2.30	0.42	1.81	0.70	3.43	4.76
HPW 441	26.46	21.92	4.00	1.05	0.26	4.00	1.20	1.11	2.50	1.05	0.80	2.00	1.25	3.90	1.20	0.31	4.00	1.40	1.43	3.31	1.20	0.92	2.36	1.40	0.90	0.23	0.90	0.35	5.27	4.24
HPW 442	26.70	21.32	4.20	2.44	0.58	5.00	2.84	5.96	12.76	2.44	2.16	5.14	2.48	4.40	2.55	0.58	6.00	2.84	6.49	13.27	2.55	2.32	5.27	2.52	2.00	0.40	1.82	0.68	2.10	3.98
HS 562	27.20	22.54	3.30	1.95	0.59	2.50	2.20	3.79	10.33	1.95	1.56	4.73	2.19	4.20	1.99	0.47	4.50	2.36	3.96	8.48	1.99	1.60	3.81	2.23	1.60	0.64	1.81	0.71	0.03	0.00
														E(S ¹)=2.29 V(S ¹)=0.149				W=0.48 χ ² = 87.10				χ ² (0.01, 6) = 16.8				Σ = 25.14 23.10				
														E(S ²)=4.00 V(S ²)=1.556								χ ² (0.05, 1) = 3.84								

Table 6: Rank based measures of stability as per original and corrected yield values for fixed effects of genotypes (2017-18)

Genotype	Yield	GAI	MR	SD	CV	Med	S _i ¹	S _i ²	S _i ³	S _i ⁴	S _i ⁵	S _i ⁶	S _i ⁷	CMR	CSD	CCV	Cmed	CS _i ¹	CS _i ²	CS _i ³	CS _i ⁴	CS _i ⁵	CS _i ⁶	CS _i ⁷	NP _i ⁽¹⁾	NP _i ⁽²⁾	NP _i ⁽³⁾	NP _i ⁽⁴⁾	Z1	Z2
HPW 349	26.51	21.35	5.00	1.25	0.25	5.00	1.38	1.56	2.80	1.25	0.80	1.60	1.75	4.10	0.88	0.21	4.00	1.22	1.21	2.66	1.10	0.74	1.80	1.47	0.70	0.14	0.66	0.24	7.60	5.00
HS 634	26.94	20.91	4.30	2.26	0.53	4.00	2.64	5.12	10.72	2.26	1.76	4.09	2.62	4.10	2.28	0.56	4.00	2.80	5.82	11.91	2.41	2.08	4.73	2.52	2.00	0.50	1.68	0.65	1.78	2.13
VL 907	26.24	22.76	4.00	2.31	0.58	3.50	2.71	5.33	12.00	2.31	2.00	5.00	2.40	3.80	2.44	0.64	3.00	3.02	7.38	19.53	2.72	2.48	7.29	2.68	2.20	0.63	2.04	0.76	3.65	7.33
HS 507	26.32	21.85	4.70	2.06	0.44	6.00	2.29	4.23	8.11	2.06	1.76	3.74	2.16	3.50	2.59	0.74	3.00	2.36	4.00	9.00	2.00	1.60	4.00	2.25	1.60	0.27	1.28	0.50	0.03	0.00
HPW 441	27.15	22.48	3.30	1.95	0.59	3.00	2.29	3.79	10.33	1.95	1.56	4.73	2.19	3.90	1.20	0.31	4.00	1.98	2.90	7.05	1.70	1.50	4.05	1.74	1.50	0.50	1.55	0.60	0.64	0.78
HPW 442	26.78	21.22	3.80	2.20	0.58	4.00	2.62	4.84	11.47	2.20	1.84	4.84	2.37	4.40	2.55	0.58	6.00	2.67	5.11	11.50	2.26	2.00	5.00	2.30	2.00	0.50	1.78	0.70	0.98	0.79
HS 562	28.23	23.56	2.80	1.62	0.58	2.50	1.82	2.62	8.43	1.62	1.20	4.29	1.97	4.20	1.99	0.47	4.50	2.31	3.82	7.82	1.96	1.60	3.64	2.15	1.60	0.64	2.09	0.83	0.00	0.02
														E(S ¹)=2.29 V(S ¹)=0.149				W = 0.44 χ ² =79.56				χ ² (0.01, 6) = 16.8				Σ=14.68 16.06				
														E(S ²)=4.00 V(S ²)=1.556								χ ² (0.05, 1) = 3.84								

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Table 7: Spearman correlation analysis among rank based measures of stability as per random effects of genotypes (2016-17)

	GAI	MR	SD	CV	Med	S _i ¹	S _i ²	S _i ³	S _i ⁴	S _i ⁵	S _i ⁶	S _i ⁷	CMR	CSD	CCV	Cmed	CS _i ¹	CS _i ²	CS _i ³	CS _i ⁴	CS _i ⁵	CS _i ⁶	CS _i ⁷	NP _i ⁽¹⁾	NP _i ⁽²⁾	NP _i ⁽³⁾	NP _i ⁽⁴⁾	Z1	Z2	
Yield	0.955	-0.901	0.057	-0.517	-0.841	0.145	0.057	-0.290	0.057	0.074	-	0.115	0.253	0.199	0.274	0.329	0.220	0.199	0.097	0.199	0.219	0.234	0.173	0.177	-	-	-	0.302	0.437	
											0.520														0.477	0.556	0.552			
GAI		-0.850	0.047	-0.519	-0.775	0.129	0.047	-0.310	0.047	0.052	-	0.094	0.376	0.163	0.286	0.433	0.206	0.163	0.133	0.163	0.205	0.241	0.120	0.191	-	-	-	0.245	0.379	
											0.519														0.444	0.545	0.525			
MR			0.039	0.601	0.926	-0.050	0.039	0.434	0.039	0.060	0.614	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
												0.039	0.015	0.071	0.081	0.114	0.084	0.071			0.071	0.103	0.060	0.032	0.065	0.645	0.705	0.696	-	-
SD				0.766	-0.016	0.957	1.000	0.610	1.000	0.947	0.750	0.969	0.271	0.853	0.843	0.286	0.870	0.853	0.571	0.853	0.869	0.856	0.764	0.863	0.620	0.537	0.534	0.408	0.410	
CV					0.499	0.720	0.766	0.782	0.766	0.778	0.985	0.697	0.060	0.599	0.550	0.039	0.604	0.599	0.504	0.599	0.599	0.596	0.532	0.613	0.870	0.843	0.845	0.032	-	
																													0.047	
Med						-0.117	-0.016	0.364	-	-	0.510	-	0.034	-	-	0.079	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.617	0.620	0.610	-	-
									0.016	0.014		0.072		0.156	0.123		0.160	0.156	0.084	0.156	0.197	0.149	0.094	0.155				0.222	0.370	
S _i ¹							0.957	0.632	0.957	0.972	0.703	0.915	0.187	0.857	0.814	0.198	0.875	0.857	0.603	0.857	0.881	0.837	0.757	0.871	0.589	0.494	0.500	0.367	0.378	
S _i ²								0.610	1.000	0.947	0.750	0.969	0.271	0.853	0.843	0.286	0.870	0.853	0.571	0.853	0.869	0.856	0.764	0.863	0.620	0.537	0.534	0.408	0.410	
S _i ³									0.610	0.690	0.798	0.555	0.123	0.512	0.436	0.147	0.524	0.512	0.688	0.512	0.508	0.490	0.458	0.533	0.736	0.680	0.682	0.224	0.143	
S _i ⁴										0.947	0.750	0.969	0.271	0.853	0.843	0.286	0.870	0.853	0.571	0.853	0.869	0.856	0.764	0.863	0.620	0.537	0.534	0.408	0.410	
S _i ⁵											0.783	0.875	0.249	0.810	0.801	0.252	0.824	0.810	0.550	0.810	0.838	0.830	0.691	0.835	0.639	0.535	0.543	0.366	0.360	
S _i ⁶												0.657	0.098	0.568	0.528	0.063	0.578	0.568	0.460	0.568	0.570	0.578	0.492	0.593	0.852	0.810	0.820	0.078	0.006	
S _i ⁷													0.253	0.852	0.834	0.286	0.864	0.852	0.607	0.852	0.861	0.828	0.779	0.850	0.560	0.493	0.476	0.403	0.405	
CMR														0.233	0.515	0.833	0.259	0.233	0.225	0.233	0.238	0.452	0.129	0.289	0.186	0.060	0.062	0.252	0.220	
CSD															0.925	0.271	0.992	1.000	0.712	1.000	0.984	0.941	0.957	0.961	0.643	0.594	0.601	0.403	0.395	
CCV																0.546	0.924	0.925	0.640	0.925	0.928	0.979	0.850	0.918	0.610	0.530	0.529	0.364	0.350	
Cmed																	0.304	0.271	0.260	0.271	0.278	0.447	0.211	0.311	0.254	0.080	0.095	0.273	0.267	
CS _i ¹																		0.992	0.732	0.992	0.990	0.947	0.933	0.978	0.636	0.567	0.589	0.407	0.420	
CS _i ²																			0.712	1.000	0.984	0.941	0.957	0.961	0.643	0.594	0.601	0.403	0.395	
CS _i ³																				0.712	0.711	0.690	0.655	0.735	0.550	0.518	0.533	0.187	0.170	
CS _i ⁴																					0.984	0.941	0.957	0.961	0.643	0.594	0.601	0.403	0.395	
CS _i ⁵																						0.957	0.907	0.989	0.624	0.551	0.572	0.380	0.393	
CS _i ⁶																								0.845	0.955	0.628	0.550	0.565	0.337	0.341
CS _i ⁷																									0.862	0.617	0.623	0.609	0.421	0.391
NP _i ⁽¹⁾																										0.644	0.552	0.584	0.370	0.388
NP _i ⁽²⁾																										0.944	0.962	0.019	-	
																													0.090	
NP _i ⁽³⁾																											0.984	-	-	
																													0.063	0.196
NP _i ⁽⁴⁾																													-	-
																													0.078	0.190
Z1																														0.961

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Figure 1: Biplot analysis of rank based measures of stability as per random effects of genotypes (2016-17)

Table 8: Loadings of rank based measures of stability as per random effects of genotypes (2016-17)

Measure	Component PC1	Component PC2
Yield	0.000	-0.387
GAI	-0.015	-0.368
MR	-0.022	0.381
SD	0.226	0.034
CV	0.185	-0.236
Med	-0.018	0.362
S _i ¹	0.220	0.049
S _i ²	0.225	0.030
S _i ³	0.139	-0.136
S _i ⁴	0.226	0.034
S _i ⁵	0.214	0.030
S _i ⁶	0.188	-0.225
S _i ⁷	0.220	0.034
CMR	-0.080	-0.053
CSD	0.230	0.064
CCV	0.228	0.062
Cmed	-0.060	-0.074
CS _i ¹	0.231	0.069
CS _i ²	0.230	0.081
CS _i ³	0.175	0.032
CS _i ⁴	0.230	0.064
CS _i ⁵	0.232	0.072
CS _i ⁶	0.230	0.067
CS _i ⁷	0.210	0.048
NP _i ⁽¹⁾	0.230	0.073
NP _i ⁽²⁾	0.145	-0.249
NP _i ⁽³⁾	0.159	-0.272
NP _i ⁽⁴⁾	0.166	-0.267
Z1	0.120	0.142
Z2	0.138	0.169
%	56.340	21.210
variance		

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Table 9: Spearman correlation analysis among rank based measures of stability as per fixed effects of genotypes (2016-17)

	GAI	MR	SD	CV	Med	S _i ¹	S _i ²	S _i ³	S _i ⁴	S _i ⁵	S _i ⁶	S _i ⁷	CMR	CSD	CCV	Cmed	CS _i ¹	CS _i ²	CS _i ³	CS _i ⁴	CS _i ⁵	CS _i ⁶	CS _i ⁷	NP _i ⁽¹⁾	NP _i ⁽²⁾	NP _i ⁽³⁾	NP _i ⁽⁴⁾	Z1	Z2	
Yield	0.958	-0.908	0.087	-0.646	-0.807	0.079	0.087	-0.235	0.087	0.040	-0.669	0.165	0.331	0.147	0.340	0.382	0.203	0.147	0.050	0.147	0.232	0.344	0.183	0.274	-0.547	-0.585	-0.570	0.187	0.200	
GAI		-0.869	0.123	-0.640	-0.785	0.098	0.123	-0.210	0.123	0.073	-0.664	0.177	0.342	0.135	0.325	0.420	0.185	0.135	0.043	0.135	0.237	0.350	0.146	0.273	-0.528	-0.587	-0.567	0.164	0.181	
MR			-0.117	0.666	0.950	-0.090	-0.117	0.291	-0.117	0.006	0.676	-0.179	-0.025	-0.131	-0.235	-0.155	-0.197	-0.131	0.069	-0.131	-0.208	-0.248	-0.156	-0.256	0.609	0.636	0.628	-0.209	-0.187	
SD				0.588	-0.090	0.980	1.000	0.373	1.000	0.950	0.556	0.940	0.239	0.835	0.801	0.203	0.829	0.835	0.163	0.835	0.840	0.817	0.806	0.833	0.499	0.516	0.529	0.380	0.364	
CV					0.641	0.620	0.588	0.535	0.588	0.660	0.976	0.495	0.055	0.490	0.335	-0.043	0.431	0.490	0.233	0.490	0.418	0.340	0.458	0.380	0.853	0.901	0.903	0.089	0.145	
Med						-0.077	-0.090	0.367	-0.090	-0.004	0.637	-0.114	0.111	-0.126	-0.161	0.060	-0.190	-0.126	0.135	-0.126	-0.210	-0.190	-0.120	-0.249	0.648	0.614	0.605	-0.202	-0.165	
S _i ¹							0.980	0.396	0.980	0.975	0.592	0.891	0.238	0.802	0.767	0.177	0.795	0.802	0.103	0.802	0.809	0.784	0.766	0.805	0.502	0.527	0.539	0.367	0.342	
S _i ²								0.373	1.000	0.950	0.556	0.940	0.239	0.835	0.801	0.203	0.829	0.835	0.163	0.835	0.840	0.817	0.806	0.833	0.499	0.516	0.529	0.380	0.364	
S _i ³									0.373	0.353	0.475	0.395	0.236	0.282	0.273	0.206	0.179	0.282	0.528	0.282	0.158	0.196	0.363	0.135	0.377	0.383	0.370	0.205	0.325	
S _i ⁴										0.950	0.556	0.940	0.239	0.835	0.801	0.203	0.829	0.835	0.163	0.835	0.840	0.817	0.806	0.833	0.499	0.516	0.529	0.380	0.364	
S _i ⁵											0.657	0.817	0.214	0.810	0.749	0.177	0.797	0.810	0.064	0.810	0.833	0.784	0.740	0.823	0.573	0.592	0.612	0.351	0.330	
S _i ⁶												0.430	0.024	0.481	0.330	-0.054	0.429	0.481	0.175	0.481	0.429	0.339	0.430	0.390	0.855	0.907	0.913	0.066	0.107	
S _i ⁷													0.233	0.779	0.764	0.174	0.788	0.779	0.296	0.779	0.759	0.747	0.804	0.768	0.406	0.423	0.436	0.396	0.398	
CMR														0.228	0.534	0.823	0.262	0.228	0.225	0.228	0.247	0.504	0.250	0.293	0.099	0.036	0.040	0.269	0.274	
CSD															0.912	0.201	0.977	1.000	0.380	1.000	0.966	0.900	0.950	0.942	0.544	0.608	0.615	0.466	0.431	
CCV																0.504	0.928	0.912	0.359	0.912	0.906	0.972	0.911	0.920	0.456	0.457	0.463	0.431	0.361	
Cmed																	0.236	0.201	0.260	0.201	0.263	0.524	0.220	0.287	0.160	-0.010	0.006	0.181	0.177	
CS _i ¹																		0.977	0.336	0.977	0.979	0.932	0.923	0.979	0.504	0.552	0.567	0.490	0.412	
CS _i ²																			0.380	1.000	0.966	0.900	0.950	0.942	0.544	0.608	0.615	0.466	0.431	
CS _i ³																				0.380	0.283	0.325	0.437	0.271	0.303	0.327	0.317	0.040	0.193	
CS _i ⁴																					0.966	0.900	0.950	0.942	0.544	0.608	0.615	0.466	0.431	
CS _i ⁵																						0.941	0.874	0.983	0.487	0.525	0.549	0.477	0.414	
CS _i ⁶																							0.850	0.952	0.463	0.443	0.462	0.422	0.352	
CS _i ⁷																									0.870	0.516	0.577	0.419	0.393	
NP _i ⁽¹⁾																										0.463	0.484	0.510	0.483	0.410
NP _i ⁽²⁾																											0.943	0.946	-0.072	-0.077
NP _i ⁽³⁾																												0.996	0.011	0.011
NP _i ⁽⁴⁾																													0.033	0.034
Z1																														0.920

Figure 2: Biplot analysis of rank based measures of stability as per fixed effects of genotypes (2016-17)

Table 10: Loadings of rank based measures of stability as per BLUE 2016-17

Measure	Component PC1	Component PC2
Yield	0.009	0.377
GAI	0.027	0.355
MR	-0.001	-0.378
SD	-0.234	-0.034
CV	-0.168	0.275
Med	0.014	-0.363
Si ¹	-0.224	-0.054
Si ²	-0.234	-0.027
Si ³	-0.057	0.129
Si ⁴	-0.234	-0.034
Si ⁵	-0.214	-0.033
Si ⁶	-0.166	0.273
Si ⁷	-0.222	-0.033
CMR	0.094	0.038
CSD	-0.237	-0.068
CCV	-0.237	-0.058
Cmed	0.078	0.086
CS _i ¹	-0.237	-0.071
CS _i ²	-0.240	-0.073
CS _i ³	-0.104	0.018
CS _i ⁴	-0.237	-0.068
CS _i ⁵	-0.237	-0.078
CS _i ⁶	-0.238	-0.063
CS _i ⁷	-0.223	-0.049
NP _i ⁽¹⁾	-0.236	-0.080
NP _i ⁽²⁾	-0.152	0.251
NP _i ⁽³⁾	-0.156	0.283
NP _i ⁽⁴⁾	-0.157	0.282
Z1	-0.112	-0.059
Z2	-0.142	-0.074
% variance	52.480	22.230

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Table 11: Spearman correlation analysis among rank based measures of stability as per random effects of genotypes (2017-18)

	GAI	MR	SD	CV	Med	S _i ¹	S _i ²	S _i ³	S _i ⁴	S _i ⁵	S _i ⁶	S _i ⁷	CMR	CSD	CCV	Cmed	CS _i ¹	CS _i ²	CS _i ³	CS _i ⁴	CS _i ⁵	CS _i ⁶	CS _i ⁷	NP _i ⁽¹⁾	NP _i ⁽²⁾	NP _i ⁽³⁾	NP _i ⁽⁴⁾	Z1	Z2	
Yield	0.42	-	0.482	0.393	-	0.482	0.464	0.607	0.482	0.607	0.429	0.464	0.875	0.464	0.607	-	0.482	0.464	0.607	0.464	0.286	0.607	0.464	0.482	0.036	0.250	0.179	0.268	0.286	
9		0.411			0.446											0.411														
GAI	1.00	-	0.268	-	-	0.268	0.393	0.286	0.268	0.286	-	0.393	0.018	0.393	0.286	-	0.268	0.393	0.286	0.393	0.357	0.286	0.393	0.268	-	-	-	0.125	0.286	
0		0.946		0.214	0.625					0.071						0.946									0.321	0.107	0.393			
MR		1.000	-	0.304	0.821	-	-	-	-	-	0.161	-	-	-	-	1.000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.411	0.196	0.482	-	-
			0.286			0.286	0.304	0.196	0.286	0.196		0.304	0.071	0.304	0.196		0.286	0.304	0.196	0.304	0.268	0.196	0.304	0.286				0.143	0.304	
SD			1.000	0.804	-	1.000	0.982	0.982	1.000	0.982	0.911	0.982	0.286	0.982	0.982	-	1.000	0.982	0.982	0.982	0.946	0.982	0.982	1.000	0.375	0.875	0.661	-	-	
				0.536											0.286													0.411	0.393	
CV				1.000	0.018	0.804	0.750	0.857	0.804	0.857	0.964	0.750	0.411	0.750	0.857	0.304	0.804	0.750	0.857	0.750	0.679	0.857	0.750	0.804	0.750	0.893	0.964	-	-	
																												0.411	0.393	
Med					1.000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.821	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.446	-	0.232	-	-
						0.536	0.482	0.411	0.536	0.411	0.161	0.482	0.214	0.482	0.411		0.536	0.482	0.411	0.482	0.446	0.411	0.482	0.536		0.125		0.250	0.375	
S _i ¹						1.000	0.982	0.982	1.000	0.982	0.911	0.982	0.286	0.982	0.982	-	1.000	0.982	0.982	0.982	0.946	0.982	0.982	1.000	0.375	0.875	0.661	-	-	
															0.286													0.286	0.196	
S _i ²							1.000	0.964	0.982	0.964	0.857	1.000	0.268	1.000	0.964	-	0.982	1.000	0.964	1.000	0.964	0.964	1.000	0.982	0.357	0.821	0.607	-	-	
															0.304													0.232	0.107	
S _i ³								1.000	0.982	1.000	0.929	0.964	0.446	0.964	1.000	-	0.982	0.964	1.000	0.964	0.893	1.000	0.964	0.982	0.464	0.857	0.714	-	-	
															0.196													0.232	0.143	
S _i ⁴									1.000	0.982	0.911	0.982	0.286	0.982	0.982	-	1.000	0.982	0.982	0.982	0.946	0.982	0.982	1.000	0.375	0.875	0.661	-	-	
															0.286													0.286	0.196	
S _i ⁵										1.000	0.929	0.964	0.446	0.964	1.000	-	0.982	0.964	1.000	0.964	0.893	1.000	0.964	0.982	0.464	0.857	0.714	-	-	
															0.196													0.232	0.143	
S _i ⁶											1.000	0.857	0.375	0.857	0.929	0.161	0.911	0.857	0.929	0.857	0.821	0.929	0.857	0.911	0.607	0.964	0.893	-	-	
																												0.304	0.286	
S _i ⁷												1.000	0.268	1.000	0.964	-	0.982	1.000	0.964	1.000	0.964	0.964	1.000	0.982	0.357	0.821	0.607	-	-	
															0.304													0.232	0.107	
CMR													1.000	0.268	0.446	-	0.286	0.268	0.446	0.268	0.054	0.446	0.268	0.286	0.018	0.161	0.232	0.357	0.339	
															0.071															
CSD														1.000	0.964	-	0.982	1.000	0.964	1.000	0.964	0.964	1.000	0.982	0.357	0.821	0.607	-	-	
															0.304													0.232	0.107	
CCV															1.000	-	0.982	0.964	1.000	0.964	0.893	1.000	0.964	0.982	0.464	0.857	0.714	-	-	
																0.196												0.232	0.143	
Cmed																1.000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.411	0.196	0.482	-	-	
																	0.286	0.304	0.196	0.304	0.268	0.196	0.304	0.286				0.143	0.304	
CS _i ¹																	1.000	0.982	0.982	0.982	0.946	0.982	0.982	1.000	0.375	0.875	0.661	-	-	
																												0.286	0.196	
CS _i ²																		1.000	0.964	1.000	0.964	0.964	1.000	0.982	0.357	0.821	0.607	-	-	
																												0.232	0.107	
CS _i ³																			1.000	0.964	0.893	1.000	0.964	0.982	0.464	0.857	0.714	-	-	
																												0.232	0.143	
CS _i ⁴																				1.000	0.964	0.964	1.000	0.982	0.357	0.821	0.607	-	-	
																												0.232	0.107	
CS _i ⁵																					1.000	0.893	0.964	0.946	0.321	0.857	0.571	-	-	

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NP _i ⁽¹⁾	-0.211	-0.037
NP _i ⁽²⁾	-0.154	0.305
NP _i ⁽³⁾	-0.203	0.131
NP _i ⁽⁴⁾	-0.202	0.142
Z1	0.167	-0.228
Z2	0.101	-0.331
% variance	73.920	14.950

Table 13 Spearman correlation analysis among rank based measures of stability as per fixed effects of genotypes (2017-18)

	GAI	MR	SD	CV	Med	S _i ¹	S _i ²	S _i ³	S _i ⁴	S _i ⁵	S _i ⁶	S _i ⁷	CMR	CSD	CCV	Cmed	CS _i ¹	CS _i ²	CS _i ³	CS _i ⁴	CS _i ⁵	CS _i ⁶	CS _i ⁷	NP _i ⁽¹⁾	NP _i ⁽²⁾	NP _i ⁽³⁾	NP _i ⁽⁴⁾	Z1	Z2
Yield	0.507	-0.679	0.429	-0.536	-0.625	0.375	0.429	0.143	0.429	0.518	0.036	0.143	0.554	0.464	0.571	0.714	0.393	0.393	0.393	0.393	0.304	0.321	0.393	0.250	-0.482	-0.286	-0.286	0.536	0.429
GAI	1.000	-0.536	0.214	-0.286	-0.732	0.196	0.214	0.036	0.214	0.161	-0.321	0.357	-0.339	0.143	0.000	-0.179	0.143	0.143	0.143	0.143	0.054	0.143	0.143	0.071	-0.446	-0.464	-0.464	0.429	0.214
MR		1.000	0.000	0.893	0.875	0.089	0.000	0.393	0.000	-0.018	0.643	0.107	-0.339	-0.071	-0.107	-0.321	0.036	0.036	0.036	0.036	0.161	0.214	0.036	0.143	0.839	0.750	0.750	-0.607	-0.321
SD			1.000	0.143	-0.089	0.982	1.000	0.857	1.000	0.946	0.607	0.929	0.232	0.643	0.714	0.393	0.964	0.964	0.964	0.964	0.911	0.929	0.964	0.893	0.375	0.393	0.393	0.214	0.357
CV				1.000	0.696	0.268	0.143	0.536	0.143	0.161	0.750	0.286	-0.268	0.000	-0.071	-0.321	0.071	0.071	0.071	0.071	0.125	0.429	0.071	0.143	0.696	0.536	0.536	-0.429	-0.214
Med					1.000	0.000	-0.089	0.304	-0.089	-0.214	0.554	0.018	-0.214	-0.411	-0.339	-0.161	-0.054	-0.054	-0.054	-0.054	0.071	0.089	-0.054	-0.018	0.786	0.696	0.696	-0.375	-0.054
S _i ¹						1.000	0.982	0.875	0.982	0.929	0.661	0.946	0.286	0.589	0.661	0.375	0.911	0.911	0.911	0.911	0.857	0.946	0.911	0.839	0.429	0.375	0.375	0.196	0.339
S _i ²							1.000	0.857	1.000	0.946	0.607	0.929	0.232	0.643	0.714	0.393	0.964	0.964	0.964	0.911	0.929	0.964	0.893	0.375	0.393	0.393	0.214	0.357	
S _i ³								1.000	0.857	0.804	0.893	0.857	-0.089	0.393	0.429	0.071	0.821	0.821	0.821	0.821	0.804	0.964	0.821	0.821	0.661	0.643	0.643	0.179	0.429
S _i ⁴									1.000	0.946	0.607	0.929	0.232	0.643	0.714	0.393	0.964	0.964	0.964	0.964	0.911	0.929	0.964	0.893	0.375	0.393	0.393	0.214	0.357
S _i ⁵										1.000	0.625	0.804	0.250	0.804	0.839	0.375	0.911	0.911	0.911	0.911	0.857	0.911	0.911	0.875	0.286	0.339	0.339	0.089	0.196
S _i ⁶											1.000	0.571	-0.054	0.286	0.321	0.036	0.571	0.571	0.571	0.571	0.589	0.821	0.571	0.607	0.732	0.714	0.714	-0.036	0.250
S _i ⁷												1.000	0.054	0.429	0.464	0.179	0.857	0.857	0.857	0.857	0.804	0.893	0.857	0.786	0.446	0.357	0.357	0.214	0.357
CMR													1.000	0.268	0.446	0.911	0.125	0.125	0.125	0.125	0.071	0.089	0.125	-0.089	-0.321	-0.339	-0.339	-0.054	-0.125
CSD														1.000	0.964	0.393	0.679	0.679	0.679	0.679	0.661	0.536	0.679	0.679	0.054	0.214	0.214	-0.286	-0.286
CCV															1.000	0.571	0.750	0.750	0.750	0.750	0.732	0.571	0.750	0.714	0.089	0.250	0.250	-0.214	-0.179
Cmed																1.000	0.357	0.357	0.357	0.357	0.304	0.214	0.357	0.143	-0.232	-0.107	-0.107	0.179	0.143
CS _i ¹																	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.982	0.857	1.000	0.964	0.446	0.536	0.536	0.143	0.321
CS _i ²																		1.000	1.000	1.000	0.982	0.857	1.000	0.964	0.446	0.536	0.536	0.143	0.321
CS _i ³																			1.000	1.000	0.982	0.857	1.000	0.964	0.446	0.536	0.536	0.143	0.321
CS _i ⁴																				1.000	0.982	0.857	1.000	0.964	0.446	0.536	0.536	0.143	0.321
CS _i ⁵																					1.000	0.804	0.982	0.982	0.571	0.661	0.661	0.054	0.268
CS _i ⁶																						1.000	0.857	0.821	0.482	0.464	0.464	0.214	0.393
CS _i ⁷																							1.000	0.964	0.446	0.536	0.536	0.143	0.321
NP _i ⁽¹⁾																								1.000	0.554	0.643	0.643	0.000	0.214
NP _i ⁽²⁾																									1.000	0.911	0.911	-0.375	-0.018
NP _i ⁽³⁾																									1.000	1.000	-0.321	0.036	
NP _i ⁽⁴⁾																										1.000	-0.321	0.036	
Z1																											1.000	0.161	

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Figure 4: Biplot analysis of rank based measures of stability as per fixed effects of genotypes (2017-18)

Table 14: Loadings of rank based measures of stability as per fixed effects of genotypes (2017-18)

Measure	Component PC1	Component PC2
Yield	-0.009	0.391
GAI	0.033	0.263
MR	-0.087	-0.382
SD	0.216	-0.115
CV	0.195	0.209
Med	-0.076	-0.349
S _i ¹	0.216	-0.098
S _i ²	0.214	-0.135
S _i ³	0.223	0.050
S _i ⁴	0.216	-0.115
S _i ⁵	0.214	-0.126
S _i ⁶	0.210	0.131
S _i ⁷	0.200	-0.101
CMR	-0.014	0.219
CSD	0.188	-0.099
CCV	0.174	-0.151
Cmed	0.002	0.202
CS _i ¹	0.228	-0.034
CS _i ²	0.218	-0.080
CS _i ³	0.208	-0.098
CS _i ⁴	0.226	-0.051
CS _i ⁵	0.228	-0.036
CS _i ⁶	0.214	-0.066
CS _i ⁷	0.213	-0.084
NP _i ⁽¹⁾	0.231	-0.007
NP _i ⁽²⁾	0.180	0.240
NP _i ⁽³⁾	0.196	0.207
NP _i ⁽⁴⁾	0.192	0.222
Z1	-0.134	-0.170
Z2	0.000	-0.185
% variance	61.850	19.080